

Spin filter effect in iron oxide nanocrystal arrays

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Abstract : Integrating nanocrystals (NCs) into magnetic tunnel structures is of considerable interest due to expectation of novel properties from their spin selective transport and single electron features. Superstructures by colloidal NCs having translational and orientational order and interesting collective magnetic properties can be prepared by solution casting through sensitive interparticle and particle-substrate interactions. In this work, we discuss the study on magnetic field induced assembly of mono-dispersed iron oxide NCs to obtain spin filter effect across the superlattice array, when sandwiched between gold electrodes. The deposition of mixed phase $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ NCs on SiO_2/Au surface proceeds through slow solvent evaporation and are studied for controlled interparticle spacing. For specific NC concentration, the ordering depends on the substrate chemistry and the ligands passivating NC surface, which affects the concentration of cluster nuclei formed. In presence of a magnetic field, the tunnel structure exhibits enhanced positive tunnel magnetoresistance at low temperatures, which could be related to their ferromagnetism and the attempts by electrons to percolate NC superlattice with preserved spin. A sign reversal for magnetoresistance is exhibited by the vertical tunnel junctions on raising the temperature.

Keywords : Magnetic nanocrystals, self-assembly, iron oxide, spin-dependent transport.

Introduction

Ordered superstructures through self-assembly using colloidal magnetic oxide nanoparticles is of fundamental and technological interest for building materials with unique magnetic and electronic properties¹. Such mesoscopic materials find use in data storage, sensing and biomedical applications. The assembly of colloidal iron oxide NCs into superstructures with translational and orientational order can be prepared by solution casting through sensitive interparticle and particle-substrate interactions^{1,2}. Narrow size distribution and uniform shape of NCs are primary requirements, besides the presence of an external magnetic field and suitable ligand chemistry. For mono-dispersed NCs, suitable ligands facilitate self-assembly into mesoscopic arrangement through bonding forces such as van der Waals attractions, steric repulsion and dipole-dipole interactions^{3,4}. They also enable superstructure growth by conducive nucleation and oriented attachment processes. In these structures, the magnetic NC dipole-

dipole interactions, magnetocrystalline anisotropy and controlled interparticle spacing lead to modified magnetic parameters such as enhanced magnetization and coercivity, not detectable in isolated NCs or randomly assembled arrays^{3,4}. In this study, we discuss the field assisted self-assembly of inverse cubic spinel iron oxide NCs with mixed-phases of half-metallic magnetite and insulating maghemite ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) compositions on SiO_2/Au surfaces by dip-coating and look into the particle interactions that order the granular system. Further, the effect of interactions towards collective magnetic properties and electron transport in NC based tunnel structure is also discussed.

Experimental

Surfactant-stabilized mono-dispersed (13 nm sized) iron oxide NCs were synthesized by two-step seeded-growth protocol based on decomposition of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ in 1-octadecene diluted mixture of oleic acid, oleyl amine, and hexadecane-1,2-diol at 280 °C, as previously des-

cribed⁵. All chemicals used were of high purity, all solvents used were of analytical grade and purchased from Aldrich. Iron oxide NC self-assembly on SiO₂/Au surfaces was carried out by dip coating a toluene solution of purified NCs (2–4 μM) through slow solvent evaporation in a toluene-vapour-saturated ambient over a period of 3 days. A perpendicular to plane magnetic field (0.5 T) was applied to facilitate growth of superlattices. Then, the substrate was extracted, washed and dried. The SiO₂/Au layers were prepared using thermal evaporation and electron beam techniques on SiO₂/Si substrates (5 mm × 5 mm).

Au (100 nm)/SiO₂/NC film/SiO₂/Au (100 nm) tunnel junctions were fabricated as cross-bar structures on SiO₂/Si wafer with junction area of 150 μm².⁶ SiO₂ barrier layers have nominal thickness of 3 nm, while Au electrodes were patterned by optical lithography using a mask aligner. In all cases, thin films of well-ordered NCs were prepared on half-junction arrays by dip coating and washing, prior to the deposition of top SiO₂/Au layers.

Characterization : Low-resolution TEM images of NCs were recorded with a JEOL TEM 1011 microscope at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV. The Fe atomic content in NC solutions were determined using inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopic (ICP-AES) measurements with a Varian Vista AX spectrometer. High-resolution scanning electron microscopy (HR-SEM) characterization of NCs self-assembled over substrates was performed with a FEI NOVA nanoSEM200 microscope at the accelerating voltage of 5 kV. Room temperature current-voltage measurements were done using a semiconductor parameter analyzer, while low temperature current and magnetotransport measurements were performed using a cryogen free magnet (Cryogenic Ltd.).

Results and discussion

Self-assembly for ordered NC arrays is investigated using 13 nm sized spherical iron oxide particles with narrow size distribution of < 5%, according to TEM images (see inset of Fig. 1(a))⁵. The mixed phase core-shelled NCs with half-metallic magnetite and more insulating maghemite compositions, Fe₃O₄@γ-Fe₂O₃, embedded in SiO₂ layers present a granular system with range of interparticle interactions decided by particle density. The oleyl amine, oleic acid and hexadecane-1,2-diol

ligands stabilizing NCs interact with SiO₂ surface through weak covalent, electrostatic adhesions and van der Waals forces, and influence the NC cluster nucleation and growth. The packing of NCs to form superlattice arrangement is also governed by the NC surface mobility. On condensing from toluene solution of NCs onto SiO₂/Au surface, the lowest energy lattice position is obtained for iron oxide assembly when NCs have sufficient diffusional freedom to move with longer diffusion lengths and reorient. The resulting assemblies are ordered with a preferred crystallographic growth direction (Fig. 1a). For comparison, self-assembly was carried out also on organically modified SiO₂/Au surfaces, where the NC mobility was reduced due to interactions between the alkyl chains of NC ligands and the organic molecules on SiO₂ surfaces depending on the polarity, resulting in less ordered structures⁵. An external magnetic field applied perpendicular to the substrate surface during solution casting is the other important parameter that helps to align iron oxide NCs into ordered patterns. In this study, for NC concentration in 2–4 μM range and applied magnetic field of 0.5 Tesla, chain shaped particle arrays with ordered close packed domains and long coherence length are observed. Fou-

Fig. 1. (a) SEM image of a self-assembled iron oxide NC array and the corresponding FFT pattern. The FFT pattern corresponds to NCs viewed down the [111] orientation of a cubic lattice or down [001] orientation of a hexagonal lattice. A TEM image is also shown as inset. (b) Schematic representation of fluctuating valences in iron oxide lattices.

rier transform (FFT) patterns of SEM imaging indicate ordering over large domains ascribed to *fcc* superlattice viewed down [111] orientation or *hcp* superlattice down the [001] axis (see inset of Fig. 1a). [111] orientation for magnetite *fcc* lattice is also one of its easy magnetic axes.

Inverse spinel cubic and ferrimagnetic Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ phases have nearly identical lattice parameters ($a_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4} = 8.35 \text{ \AA}$ and $a_{\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 8.39 \text{ \AA}$) and the outer shell in NCs ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) has few nm thickness from the preparation conditions⁵. While Fe_3O_4 has fluctuating valence states of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} ions providing electron hopping between them and magnetoresistance effects in their polycrystalline samples, single crystals and nanoparticles, $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ has vacancies in the sites of Fe^{2+} ions as shown in Fig. 1b. This causes higher electrical resistance in $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ compared to Fe_3O_4 , and provides dominant contribution towards the resistivity of NC superlattice above Verwey transition temperature (T_{Verwey}). Isolated iron oxide NCs, in the sub-25–30 nm size regime, exhibit super paramagnetic behavior and confinement effects^{1–5}. However, in the superlattice assembly of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ NCs with organic capping, each NC can be thought to have continuous ferrimagnetic spinel structure and the phases can be considered strongly interacting. Magnetic hysteresis for the assembly shows ferromagnetic features at low temperature, comparable to the values reported for mono-dispersed ferrite particles (see Fig. 2a). The collective magnetic behaviour is governed by dipole-dipole interactions, exchange coupling and thermal energy.

Lower dimensionality of particle ordering (chain-shaped array) is featured in the electron transport through NC quantized levels in the tunnel structure and described previously⁶. The electron conduction in the array occurred through discrete and parallel conduction channels, granular in nature and consisting of interparticle junctions. Hopping conduction between localized states was enhanced above T_{Verwey} (120 K in magnetite), corresponding to the localization/delocalization of valence electrons on $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ octahedral sites of the spinel. The spin dependent transport through NC arrays shows remarkable positive tunnel magneto resistance of 300% at 10 K as can be seen also from Fig. 2a. A sign reversal is observed above T_{Verwey} and a negative MR of 5–6% is seen

Fig. 2. (a) Positive TMR in iron oxide NC based magnetic tunnel junction with area $150 \mu\text{m}^2$ at 10 K below T_{Verwey} . The corresponding magnetic hysteresis loop is also shown. (b) Negative TMR obtained in the same MTJ at 165 K above T_{Verwey} upto 2 T.

at 165 K for 2 T magnetic field (see Fig. 2b). Negative TMR occurs when the magnetic moments of adjacent grains in NCs are aligned in presence of magnetic field followed by tunnelling between Fe_3O_4 core domains separated by less conducting $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ shell. The more localized carriers below T_{Verwey} in both phases and the enhanced Zeeman splitting of their electronic states facilitated by exchange coupling between magnetic domains accounts for the large positive TMR at low temperature. This is confirmed by the correlation between low magnetic field features in the TMR curve with the NC magnetization hysteresis loop.

Tunnelling of carriers through granular structure described here also involves multiple conduction paths with different sizes. At low temperatures, coulomb blockade reduces tunnelling but higher order processes involving successive tunnelling steps starts to contribute due to availability of surrounding small percolation channels^{7,8}. This successive tunnelling becomes easier when magnetic moments of the involved sites are aligned in a magnetic field. So at low temperatures and in presence of an external magnetic field, an enhancement of MR was observed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, self-assembly of mixed phase mono-dispersed $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ NCs having inverse spinel structure was carried out over SiO_2/Au surfaces. The specific organic ligands surrounding the NCs enable multiple nucleation sites and the subsequent growth of close packed nanometer-sized chain structures on SiO_2/Au surface. The electron and spin selective transport across the assembly in tunnel structures occur through discrete and parallel conduction channels. A good correlation is seen between observed TMR, its sign reversal with temperature and the iron oxide electronic structure.

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